

##Plot_Amphibian abundance_Land-use Data:

This data file contains the abundance of amphibian species in each plot under the seven land-use types.

Plotcode	Land-use.type	Village code
ME-PF1	Old-growth forest	ME
ME-PF2	Old-growth forest	ME
ME-PF3	Old-growth forest	ME
ME-PF4	Old-growth forest	ME
ME-PF5	Old-growth forest	ME
MT-PF1	Old-growth forest	MT
MT-PF2	Old-growth forest	MT
MT-PF3	Old-growth forest	MT
MT-PF4	Old-growth forest	MT
MT-PF5	Old-growth forest	MT
V13-FF	Forest fragment	V13
V13-HF	Herbaceous fallow	V13
V13-RP	Rice paddy	V13
V13-VH	Forest-derived vanilla	V13
V13-VL	Fallow-derived vanilla	V13
V13-VM	Fallow-derived vanilla	V13
V13-WF	Woody fallow	V13
V2-FF	Forest fragment	V2
V2-HF	Herbaceous fallow	V2
V2-RP	Rice paddy	V2
V2-VH	Forest-derived vanilla	V2
V2-VL	Fallow-derived vanilla	V2
V2-VM	Fallow-derived vanilla	V2
V2-WF	Woody fallow	V2
V24-FF	Forest fragment	V24
V24-HF	Herbaceous fallow	V24
V24-RP	Rice paddy	V24
V24-VH	Forest-derived vanilla	V24
V24-VL	Fallow-derived vanilla	V24
V24-VM	Fallow-derived vanilla	V24
V24-WF	Woody fallow	V24
V25-FF	Forest fragment	V25
V25-HF	Herbaceous fallow	V25
V25-RP	Rice paddy	V25
V25-VH	Forest-derived vanilla	V25

V25-VL	Forest-derived vanilla	V25
V25-VM	Forest-derived vanilla	V25
V25-WF	Woody fallow	V25
V39-FF	Forest fragment	V39
V39-HF	Herbaceous fallow	V39
V39-RP	Rice paddy	V39
V39-VH	Forest-derived vanilla	V39
V39-VL	Fallow-derived vanilla	V39
V39-VM	Fallow-derived vanilla	V39
V39-WF	Woody fallow	V39
V40-FF	Forest fragment	V40
V40-HF	Herbaceous fallow	V40
V40-RP	Rice paddy	V40
V40-VH	Forest-derived vanilla	V40
V40-VL	Fallow-derived vanilla	V40
V40-VM	Forest-derived vanilla	V40
V40-WF	Woody fallow	V40
V45-FF	Forest fragment	V45
V45-HF	Herbaceous fallow	V45
V45-RP	Rice paddy	V45
V45-VH	Forest-derived vanilla	V45
V45-VL	Fallow-derived vanilla	V45
V45-VM	Fallow-derived vanilla	V45
V45-WF	Woody fallow	V45
V47-FF	Forest fragment	V47
V47-HF	Herbaceous fallow	V47
V47-RP	Rice paddy	V47
V47-VH	Fallow-derived vanilla	V47
V47-VL	Fallow-derived vanilla	V47
V47-VM	Fallow-derived vanilla	V47
V47-WF	Woody fallow	V47
V7-FF	Forest fragment	V7
V7-HF	Herbaceous fallow	V7
V7-RP	Rice paddy	V7
V7-VH	Fallow-derived vanilla	V7
V7-VL	Fallow-derived vanilla	V7
V7-VM	Fallow-derived vanilla	V7
V7-WF	Woody fallow	V7
V8-FF	Forest fragment	V8
V8-HF	Herbaceous fallow	V8
V8-RP	Rice paddy	V8
V8-VH	Fallow-derived vanilla	V8

V8-VL	Fallow-derived vanilla	V8
V8-VM	Fallow-derived vanilla	V8
V8-WF	Woody fallow	V8

For individuals we could not identify in the field, To denote those individuals, we used “cf.” (confer or compare with) and “sp. aff.” (affinis) in conjuncture with the genus name when we found slightly different morphological characters compared with the literature that we used or compared with a given identified species. We used sp. (sp1 or sp2) in conjuncture with the genus name when we could not find any given identified species to compare with the encountered individual. The sp. denotation was thus used to differentiate several unknown species belonging to the same genus and we consider them as morphospecies

##Amphibian_Trait_Data:

This data file contains the trait data associated to each amphibian species and the source which the trait data was collected.

Extended references of the source:

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